

FIBER-REINFORCEMENT-BASED CRACK ARRESTER FOR COMPOSITE BONDED JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Development of new design features that stop cracks from growing above a critical size is one of the keys to realization of boltless structures. This study proposed a new crack arrester concept. The basic idea was that continuous fibers are introduced in the adhesive layer and massive fiber bridging suppresses the crack propagation. An x-type crack arrester was focused here and its feasibility was evaluated using double cantilever beam (DCB) tests. The apparent fracture toughness increased more than fivefold at the arrester position, and the maximum crack opening displacement doubled. Furthermore, the failure process was identified by employing X-ray computed tomography (CT) and cross-sectional observation. It was successfully confirmed that the proposed arrester concept can significantly improve damage tolerance of bonded joints, and that geometry design and material selection are the keys to further enhancement of the arresting performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bonded joints potentially possess clear advantages over traditional bolted joints. It significantly reduces the manufacturing cost related to drilling, fastening, and lightning protection. Furthermore, it allows more efficient load path with reduced component thickness and eliminates stress concentration around bolt holes. In spite of these advantages in terms of cost, weight, and performance, composite primary structures in aircraft are assembled with several tens of thousands of bolts. This is because existing bonding technologies and related non-destructive inspection techniques are unreliable (e.g., weak bond) and cannot satisfy airworthiness requirements [1, 2]. Currently, mechanical fastening is required even in bonded areas so that the bolted joints can maintain the limit load capability under the condition of global bondline failure. It is recognized that development of new design features that stop cracks from growing above a critical size is one of the keys to realization of boltless structures [3].

This study proposes a new crack arrester concept based on fiber-reinforcement. First, the basic idea is described, and its performance is then evaluated using double cantilever beam (DCB) tests. X-ray computed tomography (CT) and cross-sectional observation are employed to identify the failure process in the DCB test.

2 FIBER-REINFORCEMENT-BASED CRACK ARRESTER

The basic idea of the new crack arrester is that continuous fibers are introduced in the adhesive layer and their massive bridging suppresses the crack propagation. One example is depicted in Fig. 1. This x-type crack arrester consists of 0° and 90° composite layers cured during the bonding process (i.e., cobonded). The 90° layer is inserted between the 0° layers that are interlocked during the layup process. When a crack including the one propagating in the adherend approaches the arrester, the crack is robustly entrapped in the arrester by employing the surface ply-drop of the adherends. When the crack passes through the crossing part, one 0° layer bridges the crack and suppresses the crack opening (Fig. 1 *A*). Furthermore, the 90° layer, which is constrained by the other 0° layer, prevents the bridging layer from peeling off (Fig. 1 *B*). Thus when the crack further propagates, fibers break in the 0° and 90° layers and significant energy is absorbed. It is important to note that this arresting mechanism is effective to a crack propagating in the adherend, which is difficult to arrest by conventional approaches (e.g., toughening the adhesive itself). This is because the fiber bridging and the

Figure 1: X-type crack arrester employing interlocked continuous fibers.

Figure 2: Schematic of DCB specimen.

suppression of peeling occur even when the crack path deviates from the bondline between the 0° layer and the adherend. In a practical large-scale bonded structure, the arresters are formed along the bondline at certain intervals. Significant change of current bonding processes is not necessary for the application. It is possible to introduce the arresters by simply replacing a part of the adhesive film with stacked prepregs (i.e., arrester). Thus the cost and weight penalty is minimal.

3 VALIDATION USING DCB TESTS

3.1 Materials and methods

Performance of the x-type crack arrester was evaluated by double cantilever beam (DCB) tests following ISO 25217:2009. Figure 2 depicts the schematic of the specimen. Materials used were pre-cured unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates (T700SC/2592, Toray Industries, Inc., 3.3 mm thickness, 25 mm width) for the adherend, an epoxy adhesive film (AF163-2K, 3M), and carbon/epoxy prepregs (T700SC/2592, Toray Industries, Inc.) for the arrester. First, the 0° layers of the arrester were slit at intervals of 5 mm and interlocked as depicted in Fig. 3. The non-crossing parts were removed. The 90° layer was then inserted between the 0° layers (Fig. 4). Finally, the stacked prepregs and the adhesive films were sandwiched between the sanded adherends and cured in an autoclave. Figure 5 depicts the cross-section of the cured specimen. At the crossing point, the lower 0° layer ended, and the upper bended. The 90° layer was in contact with the bended 0° layer. At a cross-section 5 mm away from

Figure 3: Preparation of arrester.

Figure 4: Stacked arrester.

Figure 5: Cross-section of cured (cobonded) arrester.

this point, the lower 0° layer bended, and the upper ended at the middle. In this manner, the upper and lower 0° layers alternately bridged the two adherends and the 90° layer coupled them mechanically. In the following validation tests, two arrester configurations were used; Specimen *a* with two plies of the prepreg for the 0° layer and one ply for the 90° layer, Specimen *b* with three plies for the 0° layer and two plies for the 90° layer. Additionally a specimen without the arrester was fabricated for comparison.

Tensile loading was applied to these specimens through bonded hinges using a material testing system (AG-50kN, Shimadzu Co.). Loading speed was set to 3 mm/min. A crack was formed from the Teflon film implanted in the adhesive layer during fabrication. The crack reached the crossing point of the arrester after propagating 30 mm. The deformation of the specimen was recorded during the test.

3.2 Results and discussion

Figure 6 presents the load-displacement curves obtained. Without the arrester, the load gradually decreased as the crack propagated after the elastic deformation. And finally the two adherends

Figure 6: Result of DCB tests. Load-displacement curves (left) and apparent fracture toughness at arrester position (right).

Figure 7: Comparison of deformations at $\delta = 25$ mm.

Figure 8: Specimen *a* at $\delta = 50$ mm. Broken 90° layer lifted by bridging 0° layer is visible at crack tip.

Figure 9: Fracture surfaces of Specimen *a*.

separated at the displacement δ of 28 mm. In Specimen *a*, however, the crack stopped when reaching the arrester at $\delta = 10$ mm (Fig. 7), and the load inversely increased until the sudden drop at $\delta = 30$ mm due to partial breakage of the 90° layer at the crack tip (Fig. 6). The apparent fracture toughness of Specimen *a* increased fivefold at the arrester position. Furthermore, the arrester maintained the function after the load drop. The 90° layer gradually failed as the crack tip moved (Fig. 8) and the load kept the high value. Finally the specimen failed (i.e., the adherends separated) when the bridging 0° layer broke, and the maximum crack opening displacement doubled. Specimen *b* with the thicker arrester failed in a similar manner, but the load increase rate (i.e., stiffness) did not decrease until the first load drop at $\delta = 30$ mm as opposed to Specimen *a*. This result indicates that the arresting performance is controllable by changing the arrester configuration. The apparent fracture toughness of Specimen *b* at the arrester position was 18.2 kJ/m² and was seven times that of the specimen without the arrester.

4 IDENTIFYING FAILURE PROCESS

Figure 9 presents the fracture surfaces of Specimen *a*. Breakage of the 0° and 90° layers were visible, confirming that the arrester failed as expected. In order to obtain further insight into the failure process, an additional test was conducted using X-ray CT (inspeXio SMX-100CT, Shimadzu Co.). A specimen with the same configuration as Specimen *a* was prepared, and tensile loading was applied. The test was stopped at a characteristic point of the load-displacement curve, and the unloaded specimen was inspected. The DCB test was then resumed to further propagate the crack. During the inspection, the crack was kept opened by inserting a thick Teflon sheet (5 mm thickness) into the crack to observe the internal deformation when arresting the crack.

Figure 10 presents the X-ray CT images obtained. When the load inversely increased (Fig. 10 (a)), the crack tip was just at the crossing point of the arrester. And during the subsequent load increase (Fig.

Figure 10: X-ray CT images obtained at characteristic points of load-displacement curve.

Figure 11: Cross-sectional micrograph of arrester. 90° layer interlocked 0° layers and prevented them from peeling off.

10 (b)), the crack tip passed through the crossing point, and the crack path was separated into two by the upper and lower 0° layers that alternately bridged the two adherends. Figure 11 shows a cross-sectional micrograph obtained in a preliminary test. The 90° layer interlocked the 0° layers and prevented them from peeling off. As a result, intensive local deformation was induced in the 90° layer, which could lead to the breakage. After the load dropped (Fig. 10 (c)), it was indeed confirmed that the 90° layer failed. However, in some areas, the 90° layer did not break but the lower 0° layer partially disbonded from the lower adherend. This result indicates that the thickness and strength of arrester components (i.e., 0° layer and 90° layer) determine the failure process, and that geometry design and material selection are the keys to further enhancement of the arresting performance.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study proposed a new crack arrester concept. The basic idea was that continuous fibers are introduced in the adhesive layer and massive fiber bridging suppresses the crack propagation. An x-type crack arrester was focused here and its feasibility was evaluated using double cantilever beam (DCB) tests. The apparent fracture toughness increased more than fivefold at the arrester position, and the maximum crack opening displacement doubled. Furthermore, the failure process was identified by employing X-ray CT and cross-sectional observation. It was successfully confirmed that the proposed arrester concept can significantly improve damage tolerance of bonded joints, and that geometry design and material selection are the keys to further enhancement of the arresting performance.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kruse, T. (2013). Bonding of CFRP primary aerospace structures: overview on the technology status in the context of the certification boundary conditions addressing needs for development. *Proceedings of The 19th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 5635-5643.
- [2] Piehl, M. J., Bossi, R. H., Blohowiak, K. Y., Dilligan, M. A., & Grace, W. B. (2013). Efficient certification of bonded primary structure. *SAMPE 2013 Proceedings*, 58-3283.
- [3] BOPACS (boltless assembling of primary aerospace composite structures), 7th Framework Programmes, <http://www.bopacs.eu/>